

SPECIFIC CHANGES IN THE THYMUS DUE TO GROUNDWATER CONSUMPTION AND A NEW TREATMENT METHOD

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Abstract. The functions and interactions of immune cells, the complex relationships between cellular FRC and fibrillar conduction networks, which together provide the basis for efficient communication between immune cells and tissues. The physical organization of the spleen allows it to filter pathogens and abnormal cells from the blood and to facilitate interactions between antigen-presenting cells and related lymphocytes.

Keywords: compensator-adaptation, seasonal waters, underground and interstratal waters, active sulfhydryl.

The indirect impact of groundwater with high chemical content is explained by the formation of radiolysis of water, which makes up 70-80% of the body, when water is ionized, radicals are formed that have oxidizing and alkaline properties. In addition, the formation of atomic hydrogen, hydroperoxyl radicals, and hydrogen peroxide is of great importance. Free oxidative radicals enter into an enzymatic reaction, as a result of which active sulfhydryl groups are converted into inactive disulfide compounds. These biochemical processes lead to a decrease in the catalytic activity of enzyme systems, which, in turn, leads to a decrease in the amount of DNA and RNA in cell nuclei, which disrupts their renewal processes. [1,3].

The spleen mainly fights infection and also performs the following functions:

- Hematopoiesis. During pregnancy, the fetal spleen produces all the form-forming elements of the blood. After birth, the spleen produces only lymphocytes. If a person has a severe form of blood disease (for example, myeloleukemia) or bone marrow damage, the hematopoietic properties of the spleen are completely restored.

- Storage of red blood cells. This organ stores 8% of red blood cells.

- Phagocytosis. The absorption of old or decomposed cells, as well as foreign microorganisms and protein antibodies by special cells (phagocytes) is called phagocytosis.

- Immune reactions. After swallowing these antigen cells, the spleen increases production of blood-protective cells - lymphocytes.

There may be several reasons for removing the spleen during examination:

- Certain types of blood cancer. This may be a metastasis to the spleen of Hodgkin's lymphoma and non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, chronic lymphocytic leukemia, hairy cell leukemia or a tumor of any other organ.

- Other blood diseases. These include thrombocytopenic purpura (decreased platelets) and autoimmune hemolytic anemia (increased breakdown of red blood cells), and the spleen is removed when drug treatment does not help.

- Hypersplenism. This condition is caused by excessive breakdown of platelets and other blood cells as a result of an overactive spleen.

- Splenomegaly. In this case, the spleen becomes excessively large, causing pain, compression of the stomach, and specific complaints (such as a rapid feeling of satiety). To reduce such complaints and find out the causes, the spleen is removed.

- Severe injuries. In case of severe damage to the spleen and with large blood loss, when it is impossible to stop the bleeding, the spleen is removed.

The spleen is a mysterious organ. Even the ancient Greeks and Romans removed runners' spleens to increase their running speed. The functions of the spleen have not yet been fully studied. For a long time, it was considered an endocrine gland (devoid of excretory ducts). Since there is no reliable data on the secretory activity of the spleen, this theory had to be abandoned, although recently it has received a second life to some extent. Now the spleen is credited with hormonal regulation of bone marrow function. According to [5], bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BMSCs) have been identified, which are considered important regulators of immune function. Special BMSC markers were identified using flow cytometry, and successful induction of these cells into stromal cells and osteoblasts was observed.

Compared with the aging model, the spleen and thymus index were significantly increased, and the histological changes of the spleen and thymus tissues were improved. BMSCs significantly reduced the tissue damage of the aging spleen and thymus, and they could improve organ aging through the effects on cytokines, oxidative stress, and P21/PCNA. The spleen is the main filter for blood-borne pathogens and antigens, and a key organ for iron metabolism and red blood cell homeostasis [3].

However, in addition to these, it also performs immune and hematopoietic functions in mice, indicating an additional role for this secondary lymphoid organ. The spleen contains all major types of mononuclear phagocytes, including macrophages, dendritic cells (DCs), and monocytes [5]. These cells are key defenders of the body because they identify pathogens and cellular stress, remove dying cells and foreign materials, regulate tissue homeostasis and inflammatory responses, and generate adaptive immunity [2]. Research has shown that the immune system performs more than just controlling pathogens. Even without infection, the immune system can induce sterile inflammatory responses. This non-canonical function is currently the subject of much debate.

These discussions suggest that the classical role of the immune system in eliminating pathogens is only part of the overall function of the immune system. In this direction, efforts are being made to comprehensively study the role of the immune system from the point of view of physiological homeostasis [MedzhitovR. 2021]. At present, it is believed that this organ plays a central role in the regulation of the immune system, being a metabolically active organ, and is involved in the endocrine function in relation to non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. In recent years, after in-depth studies of the organization and structure of the spleen, cell functions, secretion and innervation, it has been possible to better understand the function of the spleen.

The spleen was originally thought to not only filter the blood but also to be an important center for regulating the body's immune, metabolic, and endocrine systems. However, a number of questions arose: is the spleen a player or a bystander, and what is the role of certain cytokines, adipokines/growth factors, and neurotransmitters in this complex mechanism? Adipokines have pro- and anti-inflammatory properties and play a crucial role in integrating systemic metabolism with immune function[3,5].

In other words, what is the contribution of the spleen to the development of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, is it a further manifestation of metabolic syndrome [4]. The spleen, being the largest secondary lymphoid organ in the body, performs a wide range of

immunological functions along with its role in hematopoiesis and red blood cell clearance [3,6]. The physical organization of the spleen allows it to filter pathogens and abnormal cells from the blood and facilitate unlikely interactions between antigen-presenting cells (APCs) and related lymphocytes. Spleen-specific APCs regulate the response of T and B cells to these antigen targets in the blood. There are cell types, cellular organizations, and immunological functions that are specific only to the spleen that influence the initiation of adaptive.

They help form lymphoid organ fibroblasts, specialized niches for immune cell interaction, and thereby control lymphocyte activation and differentiation. Moreover, FRCs create and coat a network of extracellular matrix (ECM) microfibers called the channel system. Channels generated by FRCs facilitate fluid and immune cell control by directing funnels of fluids containing antigens and inflammatory mediators through the ILO.

The functions and interactions of immune cells, the complex relationship between cellular FRC and fibrillar conduction networks, which together provide the basis for efficient communication between immune cells and tissues. The physical organization of the spleen allows it to filter pathogens and abnormal cells from the blood and to facilitate interactions between antigen-presenting cells and cognate lymphocytes. APCs are unique to the spleen because they regulate the response of T and B cells to these antigen targets in the blood. The spleen is the first of the immune lymphoid organs to arise in association with adaptive immunity in early jawed vertebrates. The spleen, especially its lymphoid compartment, the white pulp (WP), has undergone numerous modifications during evolution. The spleen also contains about one-quarter of the body's lymphocytes and initiates the immune response to blood antigens [PKubes2018]. This function is assigned to the white pulp surrounding the central arterioles.

The white pulp consists of three subcompartments: the periarteriolar lymphoid sheath (PALS), follicles, and marginal zone. [2,4] Histocytometric studies have shown [1,3, 8] that the spleen is surrounded by a capsule consisting of dense fibrous tissue, elastic fibers, and smooth muscles, as well as an outer layer of the capsule. The spleen consists of mesothelial cells covering it, irregularly located trabeculae of smooth and elastic tissue fibers that extend from the capsule into the splenic parenchyma [3,4]. Other authors [3,9] have shown that these trabeculae also contain blood vessels, lymphatic vessels, and nerves.

The spleen is a peripheral immune organ surrounded by a capsule of dense fibrous tissue, elastic fibers, and smooth muscle. This is what the spleen is, it is a large lymphoid organ without a cortex-medulla structure, the capsule surrounding it extends inwardly passing connective tissue trabeculae [2,7]. The outer layer of the splenic capsule consists of mesothelial cells, which may not be visible on histological section. Irregularly distributed trabeculae of smooth muscle and fibroelastic tissue extend from the capsule into the parenchyma of the spleen. The complex vascular system of the spleen plays a central role in the successful filtration of blood and the recirculation of red blood cells. Blood enters the spleen at the hilum and flows sequentially as follows: splenic artery → trabecular arteries → small arterioles → red pulp → central arterioles → small arterioles → capillary bed of various parts of the red pulp and white pulp [4] The red pulp is a blood filter that removes foreign material, damaged and dying red blood cells.

The spleen is a major filter of blood-borne pathogens and antigens, and a key organ for iron metabolism and red blood cell homeostasis. In addition, immune and hematopoietic

functions have also been demonstrated in the mouse spleen, suggesting additional functions for this secondary lymphoid organ [1,6] White pulp: BAS and lymphoid follicles. The lymphoid compartments of the white pulp include the periarteriolar lymphoid sheaths [PLS], primary and secondary follicles, marginal zone, and mantle, which vary across species [2,5].

Identification and characterization of each splenic compartment, including assessment of the relative size and cellularity of the periarteriolar lymphoid sheaths (PLS), size and maturation of lymphoid follicles, presence or absence of marginal zone cells, and the relative abundance of smaller lymphoid aggregates, are key to accurately assessing the immunologic impact on the spleen. Trabeculae also contain blood and lymphatic vessels and nerves. Lymphatic vessels are the efferent vessels through which lymphocytes migrate to the splenic lymph nodes. It follows that the spleen is a blood filter and is a highly vascular organ [4]. Blood flow through the spleen is a rather complex, but important and sometimes controversial concept. Blood enters the spleen at the hilum via the splenic artery.

The splenic artery is divided into trabecular arteries located within the trabeculae flowing into the splenic parenchyma. Small arterioles depart from the trabecular arteries and enter the red pulp, where they become central arterioles surrounded by lymphoid tissue characterizing the closed splenic circulatory system [1,4]. Along with this, the sinusoids of the red pulp of the spleen form the basis of the open type of splenic circulation, due to which it was called the cemetery of erythrocytes. Thus, as a result of our study it was established.

An important site for the clearance of exosomes and nanoparticles and can direct the emerging immune responses. In addition, it should be noted that the spleen, this small, forgotten organ, continues to surprise us with unexpected physiological functions: after the spleen was recently linked to the pathophysiology of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, the manifestation of hematopoietic function contributes to the fact that this small, forgotten organ certainly deserves even more attention from scientists in the future. It should also be noted that many issues of the structural and functional development of the spleen, and other organs of the immune system, both in the dynamics of early postnatal ontogenesis and in extragenital pathology of the mother, require further and in-depth analysis [11].

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar/Используемая литература/References:

1. Aminova G.G., Grigorenko D.E., Erofeeva L.M., et al. Changes in the cytoarchitectonics of some immune organs under the influence of toxic and medicinal substances // Actual issues of modern histopathology. -M., 2022.-P. 63-64.
2. Amosova E.N., Zueva E.P., Razina T.G. Search for new antiulcer agents from plants of Siberia and the Far East // Exp. and clinical pharmacology. 2022.-T61.-P. 31-35
3. Belenkiy M.J.I. Elements of quantitative assessment of the pharmacological effect. - L., 2000.- 148 p.
4. Belkin V.Sh. Morphological aspects of adaptation to high-altitude hypoxia. Dushanbe: Donish, 2020. 292 p.
5. Belyaev I.G. Use of licorice root extract as an adaptogen // Vestn. Ross. akad. selskokhoz. sciences 2001. - No. 5. - P. 27-29.
6. Vinogradov V.M., Bobkov Yu.G. Pharmacological strategy of adaptation // Pharmacological regulation of maladaptation states. - M., 2001. - P. 311.
7. Vladimirov Yu.A., Azizova O.A., Deev A.I. et al. Free radicals in living systems // Results

of science and technology. Series. Biophysics. M., 2022. - 249 p.

8. Galustyan Sh.D. Structure of the thymus gland in the light of experimental analysis. M., 2012.
9. Gammerman A.F., Kadayev G.N., Yatsenko-Khmelevsky A.A. Medicinal plants (healing plants): reference manual. - M.: Vysshaya shkola, 2000.-400 p.
10. Dardymov I.V. Ginseng, Eleutherococcus (to the mechanism of biological action). - M.: Nauka, 2002. 186 p.
11. Dombrovskaya E.A. Pathomorphology of adrenal insufficiency. Nalchik: "Elbrus", 2000.-231 p.
12. Durnev A.D., Sazontova T.G., Guseva N.V. and others. Effect of dioxin and cyclophosphamide on lipid peroxidation and activity of superoxide dismutase and catalase in C57B 1/6 and BALB/c mice // Bull. exp. biol. i med. 2001. - No. 5. - P. 528-532.
13. Dychko K.A., Kulagina E.V., Khasanov V.V. Composition and pharmacological activity of aqueous extract of sea buckthorn meal // Chemical-pharmaceutical journal. 2002. No. 4. - P. 32-34.
14. Elin E.E. Phenolic compounds in the biosphere. Novosibirsk: Publishing House of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2001.-392 p.
15. Eliseev V.G., Subbotin M.Ya., Afanasyev Yu.I., Kotovsky E.F. Fundamentals of histology and histological techniques. M., 2000. - 268 p.